

Acknowledgement

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References

1. M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 841.
2. M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1968, **31**, 32.
3. M. M. PATEL, M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 318.
4. M. M. PATEL, M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 773.
5. M. M. PATEL, M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 454.
6. M. M. PATEL, M. R. PATEL and B. N. MANKAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 1188.
7. M. M. PATEL and M. R. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).
8. K. NAKANISHI, *Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy*, Nankodo Company Limited, Tokyo, 1964, p. 167.
9. P. A. S. SMITH and J. E. ROBERTSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 1197.
10. R. BLINK and D. HADZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4536.
11. A. CHAKRAVORTY and K. C. KALIA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 2016.
12. K. BURGER, I. RUFF and F. RUFF, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 179.
13. A. BRAIBANTI, F. DALLVALLE and M. A. PELLINGHELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1430.
14. D. M. WILES, B. A. GINGRAS and T. SUPRUNCHUK, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1967, **45**, 869.
15. K. NAKANISHI, *Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy*, Nankodo Company Limited, Tokyo, 1964, p. 45.

Physical Properties of Iron Lauryl Sulphate and Laurate Solutions in 1-butanol

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A number of workers¹⁻⁵ have reported a considerable information about the physical properties of soaps in 1-butanol. In this note a comparative study of these properties of iron lauryl sulphate and laurate has been carried out.

Experimental

The chemicals were purified and the compounds prepared by the method reported earlier⁸. Excess of solid compounds and 1-butanol were equilibrated at different temperatures by thorough stirring. The thermostat bath was controlled to within $\pm 0.5^\circ$. Clear supernatant saturated solution was taken only when the equilibrium was attained (after 1-2 hrs) with pipette, evaporated, dried and weighed. The apparatus and procedure of conductivity and viscosity measurements were the same as described elsewhere^{6,7}.

Results and Discussion

Solubility: Solubility of compounds (Table 1) increases with increase in temperature. It is observed that the solubility of lauryl sulphate increases very slowly with increase in temperature. This behaviour is also found for laurate at low temperatures but an abrupt increase in solubility occurs at higher temperatures. The low solubility is due to its molecular state and formation of micelles in solutions increases the solubility abruptly.

The plots of $\log S$ vs $1/T$ are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a point corresponding to Krafft point i.e., 45° and 50° for lauryl sulphate and laurate respectively. The apparent heat of solution, ΔH_{so1} has been calculated by the following relationship

$$\Delta H_{so1} = RT^2 \left[\frac{d \ln S}{dT} \right] \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where S is the solubility in moles litre⁻¹ and other terms have their usual significances. The values of ΔH_{so1} below and above Krafft point are 11.44, 0.71 and 2.29, 0.17 Kcals mole⁻¹ respectively for laurate and lauryl sulphate.

Conductivity: Specific conductivity, k of solutions increases with increasing concentration at different temperatures. The plots (Fig. 1) of k vs C are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite concentration (Table 1) indicating CMC for laurate. However, the plots of lauryl sulphate are non-linear with concentration below CMC. The CMC value of lauryl sulphate solution increases with rise in temperature whereas the value for laurate is independent of temperature.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF SOLUBILITY, CMC AND CONSTANTS A AND B OF IRON COMPOUNDS IN 1-BUTANOL AT TEMPERATURES (35-50°)

Temp. in °C	Lauryl sulphate				Laurate			
	Solubility (g/100 g)	CMC (moles litre ⁻¹)	A	B	Solubility (g/100 g)	CMC (moles litre ⁻¹)	A	B
35	2.90	0.006	1.71	0.48	1.41	0.008	1.46	0.26
40	2.92	0.007	1.78	0.45	1.55	0.008	1.40	0.29
45	3.05	0.008	1.86	0.43	2.51	0.008	1.64	0.23
50	3.08	0.010	1.92	0.41	3.39	0.008	1.36	0.30
55	3.10				3.65			
60	3.13				3.86			

The molecular conductivity of soap solutions decreases as the concentration of solution increases. The plots of λ vs $C^{\frac{1}{2}}$ are concave curves which shows the weak electrolyte behaviour of the soaps.

Fig. 1. Plots of specific conductivity, $K(\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1})$ viscosity, η (millipoise) and density, $d(\text{g ml}^{-1})$ of iron compounds in 1-butanol at 50° .
 O Laurate, ● Lauryl Sulphate.

The conductivity behaviour of compounds can be represented by following relationship :

$$\log \lambda = A + B \log C \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

where A and B are constants.

The values of A and B are given in Table 1. It is evident from the data of iron lauryl sulphate that the value of A increases but B remains constant with rise in temperature. These constants show irregular variation with increasing temperature in laurate and are lower than the other compounds. This irregular variation of constant B indicates that the CMC of iron laurate is affected by temperature. Such behaviour has also been observed² in iron caprylate and caproate in 1-butanol.

Since these compounds behave as an electrolyte

in dilute solution, an expression² for their dissociation can be derived :

$$C^{\frac{1}{2}} \lambda^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{K \lambda_{\infty}^{\frac{1}{2}}}{27\lambda} - \frac{K \lambda_{\infty}^{\frac{3}{2}}}{27}$$

where K and λ_{∞} are dissociation constant and molecular conductivity at infinite dilution, respectively. The plots of $C^{\frac{1}{2}} \lambda^{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs $1/\lambda$ are linear below CMC and the equation fails above this concentration. The values of K and λ_{∞} have been obtained from the intercepts and slopes of the plots and are recorded in Table 2. The dissociation constant of iron lauryl sulphate decreases with increasing temperature and are much lower than the corresponding values of iron laurate.

Molecular conductivity at infinite dilution, λ_{∞} of iron lauryl sulphate increases with increasing temperature. This may be due to the decrease in viscosity of the solvent. The rise in temperature causes an increase in ionic mobility despite the fact that the addition of compound enhances the viscosity of the solvent. The values of λ_{∞} of iron lauryl sulphate are higher than that of iron laurate. The results confirm that micellar aggregation is affected by temperature change.

Viscosity : The plots (Fig. 1) of viscosity vs concentration of the compounds are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at CMC. The CMC values are the same as observed by conductivity measurements. Similar results are also obtained from density-concentration plots (Fig. 1).

Viscosity data has been interpreted with the aid of Vand⁸ and Moulik⁹ equations. These equations are found valid only in a limited range of concentration above CMC (Table 3). The parameters i. e., molar volume in litre mole⁻¹, \bar{v} , interaction coefficient, Q and Moulik's constants M and K' have been evaluated. Constant K' shows a reverse trend

TABLE 2—VALUES OF DISSOCIATION CONSTANT, K AND MOLECULAR CONDUCTANCE AT INFINITE DILUTION, λ_{∞} OF IRON COMPOUNDS IN 1-BUTANOL AT TEMPERATURES (35-50°)

Temp. in °C	Lauryl sulphate		Laurate	
	$K \times 10^7$	λ_{∞}	$K \times 10^6$	λ_{∞}
35	7.63	9.60	3.27	1.87
40	4.08	11.67	6.59	1.60
45	1.05	16.66	0.39	2.62
50	0.32	23.75	7.41	1.45

NOTES

TABLE 3—VISCOSITY PARAMETERS OF IRON COMPOUNDS IN 1-BUTANOL AT TEMPERATURES (35-50°)

Temp. in °C	Tested conc. range (moles litre ⁻¹)	Valid conc. range (moles litre ⁻¹)	\bar{V}	-Q	M	K'
			Lauryl sulphate			
35	0.001-.030	0.006-.030	3.91	12.77	1.11	125
40	.001-.030	.006-.030	10.14	12.17	1.23	138
45	.001-.030	.008-.030	15.66	9.89	1.33	200
50	.001-.030	.010-.030	31.32	7.36	1.53	212
			Laurate			
35	0.001-.020	0.008-.020	1.52	16.44	1.052	140
40	.001-.020	.008-.020	2.30	18.66	1.067	150
45	.001-.020	.006-.020	1.24	12.06	1.041	210
50	.001-.020	.006-.020	4.51	21.05	1.099	230

whereas other parameters (Table 3) for lauryl sulphate are higher than laurate at different temperatures.

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References

1. R. P. VARMA, K. SINGH and H. SINGH, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1978, **51**, 1530.
2. R. P. VARMA, H. K. BHARGAVA and R. DAYAL, *Ann. Soc. Chim. Polonorum.*, 1976, **30**, 307.
3. R. P. VARMA and H. K. BHARGAVA, *Ann. Chim.*, 1976, **66**, 773.
4. R. P. VARMA and K. KUMAR, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 156.
5. R. P. VARMA and K. KUMAR, *Colloid & Polym. Sci.*, 1978, **256**, 266.
6. R. P. VARMA and P. BAHADUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 1189.
7. R. P. VARMA and K. KUMAR, *Cellulose Chem. Technol.*, 1975, **9**, 23.
8. V. VAND, *J. Phys. Colloid. Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 277.
9. S. P. MOULIK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 4682.

Iodine Clock Oscillating Reaction

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Briggs and Rauscher¹ reported a new oscillating reaction, viz., oscillating iodine clock reaction. The reaction gives striking and excellent cyclic changes from colorless to gold to blue using simple reagents (potassium iodate, hydrogen peroxide,

malonic acid, sulphuric or perchloric acid, manganese(II) or cerium(III) ion and starch) in proper concentrations. It resembles the iodate-hydrogen peroxide oscillating reaction of Bray-Liebafsky^{2,4,5} and also uses manganese or cerium which are components of Belousov-Zhabotinsky^{3,4,5} reaction.

In this communication, the iodine clock oscillating reaction has been extensively studied using malonic acid and acetyl acetone in phosphoric acid medium. The concentration of each of the reactants has been systematically varied to determine the range of concentration where chemical oscillation is visible and to observe the resulting changes.

Three stock solutions are prepared separately and then mixed in equal volumes. One holds the hydrogen peroxide, another the iodate with phosphoric acid and the third, the malonic acid (or acetyl acetone), starch and manganese. This procedure has been changed when necessary and in all cases the concentrations in the table refer to concentrations in medium. The reaction mixture was continuously stirred at a more or less fixed rate with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The time period of oscillation was recorded visually.

Experimental

(Concentration ranges studied—See table)

Results and Discussion

In the sets (a) to (j) in the table, the following observations have been made.

- (a) With 0.0055(M) malonic acid—a few oscillations which are not sharp. With 0.011(M) and 0.022(M) concns.—time period decreases with time. With 0.188(M) concn.—colorless to golden oscillation.
- (b) With 0.073(M) H₂O₂—no visible oscillation. With 0.15(M) and higher concentrations—good oscillation.
- (c) With 0.043(M) KIO₃—no visible oscillation. With 0.046(M) and higher concns—good oscillation.